

SOME ISSUES OF "DOIRA" INSTRUMENT PERFORMANCE

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Abstract: This article talks about the problems of ensuring consistency between educational stages in the development of circle executive.

Key words: circle performance, children's music and art schools, unity, art and culture schools, educational stages.

Introduction.

Currently, the training of specialists in the field of music education in our republic is carried out on the basis of a three-stage system.

The first of them is the stage of out-of-school education, which mainly consists of creating basic knowledge, skills and abilities in the relevant directions of musical education in music and art schools. In addition, culture centers and "Barkamol Avlod" youth creative centers were established in order to meaningfully organize free time of schoolchildren. But the program of clubs in them does not allow to continue the next stage of study.

To build children's music and art schools and through this to form an integrated system of all-round spiritual and moral upbringing of the growing young generation, to open up the creative potential of children more widely, to promote music and other types of art. Many decisions were taken by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to create conditions for their deeper understanding and love for them, to study the national and world musical heritage. Based on this, it is necessary to further strengthen the material and technical base of children's music and art schools and increase the efficiency of their use, to equip them with new generation modern educational equipment and supplies, including multimedia educational literature and methodical manuals, local and foreign composers. Tasks such as providing music collections and pianos, as well as high-quality exhibition materials related to his work, were defined.

The second stage is through the training of junior specialists who provide secondary special information to students in specialized schools of art and culture, academic lyceums, special boarding schools in the system of secondary special vocational education (currently vocational education). is being implemented.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the activities of the Center for Secondary Special and Vocational Education of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on February 3, 2018 Art and culture colleges were transformed into specialized art and culture schools and boarding schools by Resolution No. 3504.

The goal of the activities of specialized schools and boarding schools is to educate students in specialized subjects in an in-depth and career-oriented manner, to ensure their intellectual maturity and spiritual development, and to educate them in the spirit of high

patriotism. Also, through the above decision and regulation, to organize high-quality education of students in the specialized subjects of their chosen professions in the field of art and culture in accordance with the requirements of the state education standard, in the future, higher education implementation of specialized educational programs within the framework of the state requirements that ensure high-quality knowledge and professional training in order to continue studying at the institution or engage in labor activities in accordance with the chosen profession and specialization.

The most important stage of training circle performers in musical education is the children's music and art school. The term of education for the circle executive at BMSM is five years. At this stage, the student forms the first idea about the circle instrument and learns the initial processes of acquiring performance skills. In this process, it is very important to master the performance, styles, beats (strokes) of the instrument.

Classes are conducted individually. Along with theoretical knowledge, practical performance skills are acquired.

As you move to higher classes, you should gradually move to complex measurements and exercises. In this, circle methods created and performed by master circlers together with various hand exercises, etudes, methods used in all areas of our national music culture, examples of methods performed in circle dances are presented in classes, from simple to complex, based on students' ability to perform. It is advisable to teach it in the form of note, paying attention to literacy.

As a result of our observations, it became clear that some children pass the circle class classes in music and art schools in a superficial way without observing the above-mentioned aspects. In the educational process, teaching circle methods is mainly conducted orally. This will have a negative impact on students' acquisition of notation literacy and on their comprehensive mastery of circle performance in the future. Unfortunately, there are also cases where pedagogues with other musical instrument specialties are giving lessons on the circle instrument in some children's music and art schools. We would not be mistaken if we say that this situation is the result of neglecting the circle instrument.

The next stage of training circle performers will be continued in schools of culture and art, academic lyceums for gifted children. Students study there for two years. One of the pressing problems at this stage is that they have been converted into two-year specialized schools. The reason is that the period of training in executive education at BMSM is five years. At the same time, some students in BMSMs graduate from BMSM before completing general secondary education. As a result, there is a gap between the next stage of musical education. During this period, the student forgets the knowledge he received at BMSM and has to start from the beginning at the next stage. Also, the large number of non-specialized subjects in the curriculum, the time of individual lessons related to specialized subjects, which is set at 45 minutes, prevents students from in-depth mastering of specialized subjects. The works performed by the students taking lessons from the performance of the circle should be based on the requirements of the educational stage they are studying. There are also disadvantages here.

As with any musical instrument, improving performance skills in the circle should progress gradually from simplicity to complexity. But now we can observe that the students studying in secondary schools perform the works that they should learn at the next stage of education. As a result, we witness that some students are not able to perform the work

without reaching its full potential, their performance skills are not enough. Perhaps such works are being performed depending on the talent of the student. However, it would be appropriate if the works were studied step by step on the basis of a systematic program at each stage. This situation continues in specialized art schools as well. The student learns the works to be studied in higher education during the school period. As a result, there are cases of graduates performing the works they learned at the lower level during four years of higher education. It is correct to say that the reason for this is the lack of integrity in the field of musical education. In this regard, it is necessary to establish mutual relations with all stages of musical education, to organize a systematic teaching process between them. For this, it is necessary to establish mutual cooperation of qualified specialists who work at each stage. It is desirable to systematically form executive programs.

Conclusion:

"In our opinion, it is necessary to pay special attention to the students taking lessons from circle performance in higher education, along with practical skills in performance, to in-depth mastering of theoretical knowledge related to the specialized instrument. For senior students who want to continue their studies in their field and engage in scientific and scientific pedagogical activities in the future, it will be useful to give insights about the next stage of education and educational processes in it no".

It is important to research previously unstudied aspects related to the circle instrument, to create modern educational programs, new textbooks, training manuals related to the performance of the circle.

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